

JET FLOW INSTABILITY WITH ACOUSTIC RESONANCE FEEDBACK IN AN AEROENGINE VARIABLE BLEED VALVE

Huang Huang

Tianmushan Laboratory
Hangzhou, China

You Li

AECC Commercial Aircraft Engine Co. AECC Commercial Aircraft Engine Co.
Shanghai, China

Meining Chen

AECC Commercial Aircraft Engine Co.
Shanghai, China

Jiyong Ying

AECC Commercial Aircraft Engine Co. AECC Commercial Aircraft Engine Co. AECC Commercial Aircraft Engine Co.
Shanghai, China

Qian Gao

AECC Commercial Aircraft Engine Co.
Shanghai, China

Huimin Sun

AECC Commercial Aircraft Engine Co.
Shanghai, China

ABSTRACT

Non-synchronous vibration (NSV) was detected via strain gauge measurements in a variable bleed valve (VBV) when operating at a small opening during an aeroengine test. This paper presents a numerical investigation to identify jet flow instability coupled with acoustic resonance feedback from a cavity as the root cause for this NSV. The bleeding air traversing the VBV lip throat behaves like a jet flow with a strong shear layer, which becomes unstable, oscillates and eventually sheds vortices. Moreover, the flow instability frequency is close to one of the cavity resonance frequencies. Thus, the flow instability is enhanced and coherent vortex structures are formed. To better analyze the interaction mechanisms between the acoustic resonance and the vortex shedding, dynamic mode decomposition (DMD) technique is employed to extract the coherent pressure and vortex modes from URANS solutions. Parametric studies are conducted to examine the effects of bleeding mass flow rate, VBV length and cavity volume on the aerodynamic excitation frequency and amplitude.

Keywords: Jet flow instability, Acoustic resonance, Dynamic mode decomposition, Variable bleed valve

1 INTRODUCTION

Variable Bleed Valve (VBV) in large-bypass-ratio turbofan engine serves as a critical component for enhancing compressor stall margin and optimizing engine performance across various

operating conditions. Typically installed between fan booster (low-pressure compressor) and high-pressure compressor, the VBV modulates a mount of core airflow diverted into the bypass duct by controlling its opening. This functionality is crucial during low speed operations (e.g., idle and deceleration) to prevent compressor from stall or surge.

During engine testing, strain gauge measurements revealed intense non-synchronous vibration (non-engine-order frequencies) of the VBV at an opening angle of 3° , where a narrow annular slit forms at the casing interface. The bleeding flow through the slit exhibits jet flow shear layer characteristics. The non-engine-order frequency nature rules out forced excitation from upstream or downstream rows. Notably, similar VBV acoustic resonance phenomena have been reported in the Russian's PS-90A engine [1] and Pratt & Whitney's PW1500G engine [2], despite differences in VBV design. These observations motivate our hypothesis that self-sustained jet flow instabilities through the slit clearance are the root cause of the observed NSV.

Self-sustained jet flow oscillations over open cavity have been extensively studied both experimentally and numerically [3], and can be classified into three categories: 1. pure fluid dynamic instability; 2. fluid-acoustic resonance; 3. fluid-elastic coupled instability [4,5]. Rossiter's seminal work on shear layer flow over rectangular cavities established the acoustic feedback theory and developed a semi-empirical correlation for the insta-

bility frequency [6],

$$f = \frac{U}{L} \frac{m - \gamma}{\frac{1}{K} + M} \quad (1)$$

where U is the free stream velocity, L is the cavity length, m is the mode number integer, γ is an constant for phase difference, K is the ratio of vorticity wave phase velocity to the free stream velocity, and M is the Mach number. Base on a similar concept, Thomassin et al. [7] proposed an jet core feedback theory to explain the compressor rotor NSV mechanism, in which the blade tip clearance flow behaves like a jet flow impinging to its neighboring blade and acoustic waves generated feedback to enforce the tip clearance flow. More recently, linear stability or nonlinear models are developed to analyze the instability and nonlinear mode switching mechanisms [8]. However, existing research predominantly addresses simplified geometries. This study investigates a real engine VBV geometry, emphasizing aerodynamic excitation mechanisms of jet flow instabilities while excluding aeroelastic coupling effects. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows:1) the problem statement including grid generation and CFD setup; 2) numerical solutions and DMD analyses [9,10] for the baseline configuration; 3) parametric studies of bleed flow rate, VBV length and cavity volume , and 4) conclusions.

2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Figure 1 illustrates the VBV assembly installed within the compressor flow path. The upstream inlet connects to the fan booster outlet, while the downstream exit leads to the high pressure compressor. When the VBV is open, the lip and the casing forms an annular slit, allowing core air to traverse sequentially through the slit throat into a cavity before discharging into the bypass duct. Figure 2 shows the finite element analysis (FEA) result identifying the sixth-order vibration mode (natural frequency:1759Hz), correlating with the dominant strain gauge spectrum peak observed at 3° opening condition.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Baseline Configuration

To achieve stimulation efficiency while preserving essential three dimensional flow characteristics, a quasi-three dimensional (axisymmetric) computation approach is adopted. The mesh exhibits azimuthal periodicity of 2° with 3 circumferential nodes and a total of 65,000 hybrid structured/unstructured elements. The mesh is refined in the VBV lip region and aligned with the jet flow streamline to minimize artificial dissipation (Figure3). The first off-wall distance is 4×10^{-6} m, resulting in a Y^+ value of less than 2.

FIGURE 1: VBV assembly.

FIGURE 2: Sixth-order mode shape predicted by FEA

Simulations are performed using ANSYS CFX with the SST turbulence model [11]. Inlet total pressure, total temperature and flow angles are specified according to the engine test data. Both of the two exit boundaries are assigned static pressure values adjusted to match the test bleeding flow mass rate of 4.0 kg/s. The root mean square (RMS) residual is reduced more than three orders of magnitude to ensure convergence. As shown in the Mach Number and vorticity contour (Figure 4), the flow field exhibits an attached boundary layer development along the VBV lip without separations. Furthermore, a distinct shear layer forms between the high speed jet flow and the nearly stagnant cavity flow due to their significant velocity difference.

Unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) computations with a physical time step of 5×10^{-6} s are performed. The initial condition is the previous converged steady solution. A pressure sensor is positioned near the VBV lip to

FIGURE 3: Hybrid quasi-three-dimensional mesh.

FIGURE 4: Mach number (up) and Vorticity (down) contours near the VBV lip

monitor the unsteady computation. The time history of the static pressure (Figure 5) exhibits an exponential amplification at the initial stage, indicating linear instability. And the fluctuation pressure eventually reaches a limit cycle oscillation (LCO) due to its intrinsic damping. Fast Fourier transform (FFT) analysis of the last 10000 time steps reveals dominant frequency peaks

at 1559Hz and its second harmonic (Figure 6). Instantaneous vorticity (Figure 7) contour highlights coherent vortex structures.

FIGURE 5: Static pressure time history

FIGURE 6: FFT of static pressure

In order to analyze the pressure and vortex modes, last two cycles of LCO pressure and vorticity snapshots are post-processed using DMD. Figure 8 illustrates the amplitude and phase of the dominant pressure mode at 1559 Hz. Dark blue lines within the cavity, known as wave nodes, indicate regions of minimal pressure fluctuation. The phase difference across nodes is approximately 180° , while the phase remains nearly constant within each node region, indicating a nearly standing acoustic wave. Additionally, dominant pressure fluctuations occur near the VBV lip, contributing to NVS. Figure 9 displays the real and imaginary parts of the vortex mode. Note that the initial disturbance originates in the sudden expansion region, driven by the

FIGURE 7: Instantaneous vorticity contour

shear layer instability between the high speed jet flow and the quiescent upper flow.

3.2 Effects of Bleeding Mass Flow Rate

In this subsection, the effects of the bleeding mass flow rate on the jet flow instability are investigated to determine whether the frequency can be shifted from the VBV vibration natural frequency or the pressure fluctuation amplitude can be reduced. By adjusting the VBV outlet pressure, the mass flow rate and jet flow velocity are varied accordingly. Table 1 summarizes the four cases considered, with case 1 and 2 below and case 3 and 4 above the baseline mass flow.

Figure 10 compares steady pressure contours as well as velocity vectors for the baseline configuration, case 1, case 3 and case 4. The solution for case 2 is not shown as it is similar to case 1. For the lowest mass flow rate case (case 1), the velocity vector upstream of the VBV lip is directed downward, the boundary layer flow on the VBV lower side reverses. The incidence angle is negative, as also reflected in the pressure contour. The baseline case shows near-zero incidence, with the boundary layer on both the VBV lower and upper sides attached without separation. In case 3, the incidence angle becomes positive, and no separation occurs either. However, as the mass flow increases further in case 4, the high incidence angle results in significant boundary layer separations on the VBV upper side, which is more evident

TABLE 1: Four different bleeding mass flow cases.

	case 1	case 2	case 3	case 4
mass flow (kg/s)	1.96	2.68	5.17	6.26

FIGURE 8: Pressure mode amplitude and phase

in the steady Mach number contour (Figure 11).

Next, unsteady computations are conducted. It is found that the instability frequency remains the same for case 1-3. However, the jet flow instability disappears in case 4 due to the changes in the shear layer at the high incidence angle. Figure 12 and Figure 13 compare the DMD pressure and vortex modes for case 1 and case 2. As mass flow decreases, both pressure and vortex fluctuations weaken compared to the baseline (Figure 8 and Figure 9). Additionally, as the incidence angle becomes negative, vortices on the VBV lower side strengthen relative to the upper side. Although the pressure mode amplitude varies for these cases, the mode shape remains almost identical. Therefore, jet flow oscillations are all locked into the cavity acoustic mode except for the highest mass flow (case 4).

FIGURE 9: Vortex mode real (up) and imaginary (down) part

3.3 Effects of VBV length

Previous studies on edge tone suggest that the distance from the slit to downstream edge significantly influences the instability frequency [12]. In current study, the VBV length is modified by extending and shortening the trailing edge while keeping mass flow rate unchanged. Unsteady computations reveal single dominant frequencies at 1739 Hz for the extended VBV and 1499 Hz for the shortened VBV. Figure 14 compares the DMD pressure mode for the long and short VBVs. The higher frequency mode exhibits smaller scale structures, while the lower frequency mode has larger scale structures. The instability frequency follows the trend: Long VBV > baseline VBV > short VBV. Thus, the Strouhal number is not constant for different VBV length cases. This can be explained by the vortex contours (Figure 15). The number of coherent vortex on the VBV switches to 5 in the long VBV, 3 in the short VBV, and 4 in the baseline VBV (Figure 7). Similar to the edge tone phenomena, the jet flow instabil-

FIGURE 10: Comparison of static pressure contour and velocity vector

FIGURE 11: Steady Mach number contour for case 4

ity shifts between different stages and locks into distinct cavity acoustic frequencies when changing the VBV length.

3.4 Effects of Cavity Volume

Cavity resonance frequency depends on its volume and shape. In this subsection, the cavity volume to altered by either elevating or lowering the cavity upper wall (Figure 16). This modification minimally affects steady flow near the VBV lip, meaning any observed frequency shifting should originate solely from changes in the cavity acoustic mode.

FIGURE 12: Pressure mode for case 1 (right) and case 2 (left)

FIGURE 13: Vortex mode for case 1 (right) and case 2 (left)

For the large cavity, a static pressure probe at the baseline location captures beat phenomena in the time history (Figure 17), which is also verified by the short-time FFT solutions. In the initial 10,000-20,000 cycles, the 1559Hz frequency dominates while 2039Hz is minor. But later, both frequencies are co-existing along with sub-harmonics and high harmonics. The DMD pressure modes are shown in Figure 18. The 1559 Hz mode exhibits high pressure fluctuations in the VBV lip region; while the 2039Hz mode has high pressure fluctuations in the cavity corner. Also note that the higher frequency mode corresponds to smaller coherent scale and vice versa. The real part of DMD vortex modes shows a similar scaling, with the 2039Hz vortex mode amplitude being weaker (Figure 19).

For the small cavity, the static pressure time history and short-time FFT solutions are shown in Figure 20. The initial disturbance is 1559Hz, which later shifts to 1779Hz. The DMD pressure mode at 1779Hz also has dominant pressure fluctuations near the VBV (Figure 21), but its shape differs from the 1559Hz mode. A comparison between the 1779Hz vortex mode (Figure 22) with 1559 Hz vortex mode reveals differences in vortex pairing. The 1779 Hz mode exhibits 5.5 pair of vortex on the VBV, whereas the 1559 Hz mode has 5 pair. This suggests that jet flow vortex modes are influenced by the cavity acoustic resonance.

FIGURE 14: Pressure mode for the long (up) and short (down) VBV

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This study investigates jet flow instability and its interaction with cavity acoustic resonance in a variable bleed valve (VBV). Numerical simulations and dynamic mode decomposition (DMD) analyses identify key mechanisms showing that cavity acoustic resonance significantly influences jet flow behavior, affecting vortex frequency and structures. Parametric studies on mass flow rate, VBV length, and cavity volume provide insights into instability control. These findings contribute to optimizing VBV design and mitigating non-synchronous vibrations in turbofan engines.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We are grateful for the fruitful discussions with Dr. Jinzhang Feng at AECC Commercial Aircraft Engine Co.

FIGURE 15: Instantaneous vortex for the long (up) and short (down) VBV

FIGURE 16: Large (left) and small (right) cavity mesh

REFERENCES

- [1] Aleksentsev, A., Sazhenkov, A., and Sukhinin, S., 2016. "Acoustic resonance phenomena in air bleed channels in aviation engines". *Journal of Applied Mechanics and Technical Physics*, **57**(6), pp. 971–978.
- [2] Hunsberger, R., March 4, 2022. "Aviation investigation-4 docket items: Eng19ia034". *Aviation Investigation-4*

FIGURE 17: Static pressure time history and FFT for large cavity

Docket Items: ENG19IA029.

- [3] Colonius, T., 2001. "An overview of simulation, modeling, and active control of flow/acoustic resonance in open cavities". In 39th Aerospace Sciences Meeting and Exhibit, p. 76.
- [4] Rockwell, D., and Naudascher, E., 1978. "Self-sustaining oscillations of flow past cavities". *Journal of Fluids Engineering*, **100**(2), pp. 152–165.
- [5] Rockwell, D., and Naudascher, E., 1979. "Self-sustained oscillations of impinging free shear layers". *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics*, **11**, pp. 67–94.
- [6] Rossiter, J., 1964. "Wind-tunnel experiments on the flow over rectangular cavities at subsonic and transonic speeds". *Aeronautical Research Council Reports and Memoranda*, **3438**.
- [7] Thomassin, J., Vo, H. D., and Mureithi, N. W., 2009. "Blade tip clearance flow and compressor nonsynchronous vibrations: the jet core feedback theory as the coupling mechanism". *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **131**(1).
- [8] Hong, Z., Wang, X., Jing, X., and Sun, X., 2020. "Frequency lock-in mechanism in flow-induced acoustic resonance of a cylinder in a flow duct". *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, **884**, p. A42.
- [9] Schmid, P. J., and Sesterhenn, J., 2010. "Dynamic mode decomposition of numerical and experimental data". *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, **656**(10), pp. 5–28.
- [10] Demo, N., Tezzele, M., and Rozza, G., 2018. "Pydmd: Python dynamic mode decomposition". *The Journal of Open Source Software*, **3**(22), p. 530.

FIGURE 18: 1559 Hz pressure mode (up) and 2039Hz pressure mode (down) for large cavity

- [11] Menter, F. R., 1994. "Two-equation eddy-viscosity turbulence models for engineering applications". *AIAA Journal*, **32**.
- [12] Curle, N., 1953. "The mechanics of edge-tones". *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A. Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, **216**(1126), pp. 412–424.

FIGURE 19: 1559 Hz vortex mode (up) and 2039Hz pressure mode (down) for large cavity

FIGURE 20: Static pressure time history and FFT for small cavity

FIGURE 21: 1779 Hz pressure mode for small cavity

FIGURE 22: 1779 Hz vortex mode for small cavity